

EXTRALINGUISTIC ISSUES IN CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATION: ATTITUDES, RITUALS, TRADITIONS

Scientific supervisor: **Abdulazizov Davudbek.**

Institute of Foreign Languages of Andijonda region

319 group students

Shamsutdinova Nozima

Abstract: *Cross-cultural communication is the process of sharing information between people from different cultures. It is important to remember that each culture has its own set of values, beliefs, and norms, which can impact the way information is interpreted. When communicating with someone from another culture, it is essential to be aware of these differences and to adjust your communication style accordingly.*

Key words: *cross-cultural, formal language, transmit, nonverbal, barrier, globalized society, implication.*

Culture is a way of thinking and living whereby one picks up a set of attitudes, values, norms and beliefs that are taught and reinforced by other members in the group. This set of basic assumptions and solutions to the problems of the world is a shared system that is passed on from generation to generation to ensure survival. A culture consists of unwritten and written principles and laws that guide how an individual interacts with the outside world. Members of a culture can be identified by the fact that they share some similarity. They may be united by religion, by geography, by race or ethnicity. Cross cultural communication thus refers to the communication between people who have differences in any one of the following:

styles of working, age, nationality, ethnicity, race, gender, sexual orientation, etc. Cross cultural communication can also refer to the attempts that are made to exchange, negotiate and mediate cultural differences by means of language, gestures and body language. It is how people belonging to different cultures communicate with each other. Each individual can practice culture at varying levels. There is the culture of the community he grows up in, there is work culture at his work place and other cultures to which one becomes an active participant or slowly withdraws from. An individual is constantly confronted with the clash between his original culture and the majority culture that he is exposed to daily. Cultural clashes occur as a result of individuals believing their culture is better than others. Cross cultural communication has been influenced by a variety of academic disciplines. It is necessary in order to avoid misunderstandings that can lead to conflicts between individuals or groups. Cross cultural communication creates a feeling of trust and enables cooperation. The focus is on providing the right response rather than providing the right message. When two people of different cultures encounter each other, they not only have different cultural backgrounds but their systems of turn – talking are also different. Cross cultural communication will be more effective and easier if both the speakers have knowledge of the turn taking system being used in the conversation (For example: One person should not monopolize the conversation or only one person should talk at a time).

- 1) Assumption of similarities : This refers to our tendency to think how we behave and act is the universally accepted rule of behavior. When someone differs, we have a negative view of them.

- 2) Language Differences : Problems occur when there is an inability to understand what the other is saying because different languages are being spoken. Talking the

not prejudice a person or stereotype them. By accepting people and their differences and acknowledging that we don't know everything will make us open up to people and their differences resulting in us using contextual information for better understanding. Seeking feedback and taking risks to open up channels of communication and being responsible for our feelings and actions will go a long way in ensuring that miscommunication is mitigated.

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